

"Boosting Sustainable Tourism Development and Capacity of Tourism SMEs through Transnational Cooperation and Knowledge Transfer"

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3. Association Des Villes Et Regions Pour La Gestion Durable Des Ressources / ACR+ (Belgium)

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D4.1 Report on scheme implemented

WP4 Implementation of support schemes

TOURISME

Boosting Sustainable Tourism Development and Capacity of Tourism SMEs through Transnational Cooperation and Knowledge Transfer

TOURISME

Improving sustainability of tourism SMEs through knowledge transfer, international cooperation and multi-stakeholder engagement

D4.1 Report on scheme implemented

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Abbreviations

B2B Business to Business

NACE Nomenclature of Economic Activities

SDG Sustainable Development Goals

SME Small and Medium Enterprise

WP Work Package

D Deliverable

1.Introduction

1.1 TOURISME project introduction

This report (Deliverable D4.1) was prepared in the context of **Work Package 4 (WP4) “Implementation of the support schemes”** of the TOURISME project.

In the EU, tourism is one of the major economic activities with a high impact on economic growth, employment, and social development, and thus it is a powerful means to pursue broader EU employment and growth objectives. The competitiveness of the European tourism industry is closely linked to its sustainability, understood as environmental, economic, and socio-cultural aspects of tourism development. Achieving sustainable tourism development can bring numerous benefits derived from the competitive advantage provided by cost savings and the improvement of the quality of the offer. In this sense, to achieve sustainability and improve competitiveness, TOURISME has aimed at fostering SMEs’ capacities and skills to explore and uptake solutions through a reinforced transnational and cross-sectoral collaboration amongst tourism SMEs and operators in 3 core countries - Spain, Italy, France, plus an optional one - Cyprus.

More specifically, the objectives of TOURISME have been the following:

- To design and implement trans-national and cross-sectoral support schemes including capacity building knowledge;
- transfer and scaling-up activities to enable sustainable growth of SMEs in the tourism sector;
- To support the uptake of innovative solutions for sustainable tourism;
- To support the participation of SMEs in certification schemes.

Scaling-up SMEs’ activities and building their capacities through knowledge transfer, exchanges and collaboration with other SMEs and other tourism industry stakeholders across sectors and nations

Supporting the **uptake of innovative solutions** that boost sustainable practices and circular business models, addressing the growing consumer demand for an eco-friendlier tourism experience

Supporting participation of SMEs in **environmental certification schemes and other initiatives** that promote sustainable tourism and that lead to competitive advantages, such EU Ecolabel

1.2 SMEs’ recruitment and engagement

To fulfil the objectives of the project, the project designed a Call for SMEs open to small and medium sized businesses operating in the tourism sector under different business activity codes as shown in the figure below.

Hotels and similar accommodation
(NACE 55.1)

Holidays and other short-stay accommodation
(NACE 55.2)

Travel agencies, tour operator reservation service and related activities
(NACE 79)

The Call for SMEs was launched in three phases under WP3 (<https://tourisme-project.eu/call-for-smes>) to select at least 60 SMEs from 3 official project countries (Spain, Italy, and France), plus additional SMEs from a fourth optional country (Cyprus).

TOURISME awarded 65 SMEs which signed agreements with the relevant project partners to receive Third Party Financing Support:

- Spain: 21;
- Italy: 21;
- France: 20;
- Cyprus (optional country): 3.

The awarded SMEs were involved in project support schemes implemented through WP4 and which are described subsequently.

1.3 Supporting schemes for SMEs

WP4 has dealt with the organisation and implementation of the support schemes developed in WP3. These activities involve the financial support to the awarded SMEs managed by ITC (Spain), SFC, RAS (Italy), L'InstParisReg (France), and ANEL (Cyprus).

The support schemes planned under TOURISME were three, executed across three tasks of WP4:

T4.1 Face-to-face/online capacity building trainings and mentoring

T4.2 Matchmaking SMEs (B2B)

T4.3 Access to environmental certifications

- **Training Voucher - Task 4.1. Face-to-face and online capacity building trainings and mentoring.** This task foresaw the organisation of workshop training/mentoring sessions to increase the skills of the SMEs and facilitate scaling-up of sustainable growth and uptake of innovative solutions. During the implementation phase, four training sessions were delivered in Spain, Italy, France, and Cyprus. Topics addressed were adapted according to local needs and preferences expressed by SMEs across the different countries.
 - *Type of financial support:* Each beneficiary SME received financial support in the form of a Training Voucher valued for EUR 2,000 if based in Spain, France or Italy (on average, EUR 500 per face-to-face training), or EUR 1,200 if in Cyprus (EUR 300 per training).
 - *Type of costs covered:* National travel expenses to participate in training activities, including transportation, accommodation, and daily allowance.

- **Matchmaking Voucher - Task 4.2. Matchmaking SMEs.** Matchmaking of SMEs was aimed at creating synergies business-to-business (b2b) to facilitate the exchange of good practices among SMEs and with technology and sustainable solutions providers, fostering networking and technical cooperation. Two matchmaking events were organised in Spain (ITC), Italy (SFC, RAS), and France (L'InstParisReg) where, in order to reduce costs these events have been in some cases organised in conjunction with fairs or conferences taking place at the time, if relevant.
 - *Type of financial support:* Each beneficiary SME received financial support in the form of a Matchmaking Voucher valued for EUR 4,000 if based in Spain, France or Italy (on average, EUR 2,000 per event), or EUR 2,200 if in Cyprus (EUR 1,100 per event).
 - *Type of costs covered:* International travel expenses to participate in matchmaking activities, including transportation, accommodation and daily allowance.

- **Certifications Voucher - Task 4.3 Access to environmental certifications.** This task was aimed to facilitate access to different environmental certifications and EC initiatives promoting sustainable tourism, such as the EU Ecolabel. The selection of working with environmental certifications was optional, upon request of the SMEs during the funds' application process. The activities were carried out through, on the one hand, face-to-face workshops within task 4.1, and additional tailored supporting and advisory sessions embedded within the matchmaking events and/or provided b2b by project partners to their SMEs.
 - *Type of financial support:* Each beneficiary SME received financial support in the form of a Certification Voucher valued for EUR 1,000 if based in Spain, France or Italy, or EUR 600 if in Cyprus.
 - *Type of costs covered:* Individual mentoring and advisory services from experts, consultants, and certification providers, as well as costs of certification or standardisation.

Amounts of TOURISME financial schemes reported for each voucher above were indicative and have been adapted to the real cost of each activity.

1.4 Deliverable 4.1 scope

The scope of the present deliverable (D4.1) is to provide a comprehensive outline of the **methodology, participation, activities, and main outcomes from the implementation of the schemes under tasks 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3.** The report also serves to present main conclusions, challenges, lessons learnt from the

TOURISME experience, serving future similar initiatives and projects to increase support for tourism SMEs towards enhanced sustainability. The outcomes of this report have fed the establishment of Replication Guidelines in D6.4 under WP6.

D4.1 report is structured in 5 sections. Section 2 reports the approach and activities implemented for the first support scheme of training. Similarly, Section 3 describes the methods and programmes of the matchmaking events organised within the second support scheme along with the participation achieved, and the main results and lessons learnt. Section 4 provides an aggregated overview of the actions and outcomes of the third support scheme aimed at facilitating access to environmental certifications. Section 5 is a conclusive section to report on the project experience's overall outcomes, the impacts obtained through the support schemes implemented, and the feedback retrieved from the involved SMEs. Also, this section lays down the key next steps for **sustainability** discussed with SMEs in each of the project countries and recommendations for future **exploitation**. Finally, attached to the deliverable are the main relevant templates developed under WP4.

2. Support scheme #1: training

Face-to-face/online
capacity building
training

Under task 4.1, four training sessions were delivered in each of the TOURISME countries, respectively by: L'InstParisReg in France, RAS & SFC in Italy, ITC in Spain, and ANEL in Cyprus. Training sessions were usually implemented in either a hybrid mode or face-to-face depending on the logistics capabilities of partners and preferences of SMEs to ensure spending of training vouchers by SMEs. At least one of the trainings had to tackle, partially or entirely, the topic of certifications to support the execution of task 4.3.

As an initial step of task 4.1, WP4 leader CE produced common task 4.1 guidelines, a calendar template shared with all relevant partners, and a template for training report. CE also developed a survey template to be distributed among SMEs in order to collect qualitative information on the training implemented, to assess satisfaction, and to gather feedback for activities' improvement. Partners were requested to fill out the developed Report Template after each of their training sessions to summarise activities implemented and results achieved. WP4 Leader organised an online technical workshop with the relevant project partners financing on 30th November 2021 to establish a common approach for the execution of the training activities. Afterwards, it ensured periodic checks on task 4.1 progression in joint project meetings and b2b individual updates with each of the 5 partners in charge of delivering the support scheme's activities.

Each project country had to deliver 4 training actions (with a minimum duration of approx. 4 hours) with the provision of practical and technical information with deeper and deeper details and explanations as long as the training path was proceeding. Without major restrictions, the partners delivering the training support schemes had to:

1. Introduce concept and frameworks of sustainable tourism;
2. Share and discuss good practices including those addressed in the TOURISME Compendium, experiences and case studies on sustainable tourism to help SMEs establish their sustainable path and strategy to start implementing or modifying certain habits and processes to reduce their environmental impact; and
3. Provide knowledge on environmental certification and eco label schemes and procedures.

A description of the implemented activities per country is provided below.

2.1 France

Four training actions in France, plus an additional introductory online meeting, have been carried out by the Institute Paris Region (L'InstParisReg) partner under task 4.1.

The objective of the first part of French training path (first 2 sessions; 15 hours) was devoted to acquiring the essential notions related to sustainable tourism (carbon footprint, impacts on biodiversity, circular economy, notion of responsible tourism, etc.). The specific objectives were to:

- know the networks of competent actors such as ADEME, labelling organisations, carbon offsetting organisations;
- know the potential aid and funding sources;
- get methodological support so that each participant can have the necessary tools to implement actions in its company in small group workshops;
- promote a workgroup dynamic facilitating the production of ideas and possible solutions for participants' own business.

The other part of the training (2 last sessions; 18 hours) was aimed at providing more details about increased sustainability in SMEs' daily processes, uptake of new actions and sharing of best practices for replication. In particular, training addressed environmental certifications and reduction of digital footprint. The rationale behind the choice of certifications was that awarded French SMEs were ready to take into account changes towards sustainability and willing to access environmental certifications; however, almost all of them SMEs did not have any previous background or experience in this regard. The aim was to provide an overview of the most common certification and labels regarding sustainable tourism and acquire the essential knowledge on the different steps and costs of eco certification. L'InstParisReg focused on the following certifications: EU ECO label, Green Key, Travel Life, ATR French Label, and Constructions labels. On the other hand, the topic of digital footprint emerged as particularly relevant for participants, considering the era of digital transformation SMEs are experiencing.

2.1.1 Kick off meeting

On 22nd December 2021, a first online kick off webinar with the SMEs was implemented as an introductory event to present the TOURISME project, discuss the Third-Party Beneficiary Agreement, and agree on the training calendar and following steps and dates for the support scheme activities. L'InstParisReg opted for the organisation of this extra activity, beyond the four training sessions, to allow SMEs to meet each other for the first time and dedicate some time to explain the TOURISME support schemes and the administrative aspects of the functioning of the EC Financial Support for Third Parties (FSTP).

Date	Place	Programme
22/12/2021	Online	Presentation of the L'InstParisReg Presentation of the awarded SMEs Training planning Certification activity and voucher Administrative details Third-Party Beneficiary Agreement signature

2.1.2 First training

On 21st March 2022, the first training action was delivered focusing on fundamentals of sustainable tourism and presenting the tourism carbon footprint in France, its challenges, and the limits of carbon offsetting. The action also promoted the application of the circular CANVAS method to tourism companies. This method was used in a series of group workshops on the themes identified in the call for SMEs: environmental awareness, implementation of specific sustainable practices, and development of a sustainable business strategy.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
21/03/2022	Paris (face-to-face only)	17	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation of the training courses and calendar, administrative aspects ▪ Reverse presentation of participants ▪ Sustainable tourism: principles, basis and implementation ▪ Carbon footprint of tourism in France, challenges and limits of carbon offsetting ▪ Circular CANVAS method applied to tourism companies ▪ Group workshops on the themes identified during in the call for SMEs applications: awareness, implementation of specific practices, development of a sustainable business strategy

Figure 1. First French training

2.1.3 Second training

The second training action was organised on 22nd and 23rd March 2022. It was focused on the first day, on fundamentals of waste, energy & water savings, and green procurements and completed by workshops on the topic of sustainable accommodations based on the experience of participating SMEs. The training focused on how to structure energy saving strategy, promoting a decarbonized mobility & circular economy approach, and controlling waste production. On the second day, additional workshops – where each participant presented their roadmap of sustainable tourism – were conducted. The activities were followed by a study visit to the ZAZIE Hotel in Paris, a good practice of low carbon footprint tourism structure.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
22-23/03/2022	Paris (face-to-face only)	17	<p><i>22nd March 2022</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ How to structure your energy saving strategy ▪ Promoting a decarbonized mobility: tracks and perspectives ▪ Circular economy introduction and approaches for tourism SMEs ▪ Controlling waste production <p><i>23rd March 2023</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation of corporate social responsibility (CSR) aspects ▪ Interactive workshops ▪ Study visit to ZAZIE Hotel, a good practice of sustainable accommodation

Figure 2. Second French training and study visit

2.1.4 Third training

On 17th and 18th May 2022, the third training action addressed access to environmental certifications. The aim was to get an overview of the most common certification and labels regarding sustainable tourism and acquire the essential knowledge on the different steps and costs of eco certification. The training reviewed EU ECO labels, Green Key, Travel Life, ATR French Label, and Constructions labels. This action aimed at raising awareness among SMEs of the importance of the territorial dimension of labels and started thinking about their certification path, also supported in certain cases by the TOURISME voucher. The training was organised in conjunction with the first international matchmaking event in France, held on 16th May, to achieve the greater attendance in the matchmaking and allow French SMEs to meet their international peers.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
17-18/05/2022	Paris & online	22	<p>17th May 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Green Key Label ▪ ATR Label ▪ Travel Life Label ▪ European ECO Label ▪ Sustainable construction and frugal building ▪ Territorial approach of the labelling <p>18th May 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Administrative aspect: financial and technical report to be provided by SMEs ▪ Digital best practices

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Group workshop on sustainable IT practices. 4 groups: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improved email management 2. Re-design or update website in eco-design 3. Switch from travel diary to e-travel diary 4. Social networks - how to better communicate and optimise posts & newsletters
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Figure 3. Third French training

2.1.5 Forth training

On 14th October 2022, the fourth and last training action was organised in conjunction with the international matchmaking event (13th October) to encourage international networking and b2b matchmaking. Interestingly, the training used a special format known as the “**Fresco of climate**” approach for the SMEs workshop, adapted to acquire the main notions relating to climate change issues. Workshop work was carried out in three groups:

1. use of cards representing the main issues of climate change;
2. definition of the relation in terms of causes and consequences between these different elements;
3. co-construction of the global view in each group; and
4. presentation of the fresco including each participant on their vision of their activities and especially in the long run.

Besides the workshop, practices and experiences in sustainable tourism management were put in common by attending SMEs to encourage peer learning.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
14/10/2022	Paris (face-to-face only)	20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The climate fresco workshop ▪ Presentation of results of actions and practices undertaken by participating SMEs

Figure 4. Fourth French training and the “Fresco of Climate” workshop

2.2 Italy

Training actions in Italy have been jointly implemented by the Region of Sardinia (RAS) and Sistemi Formativi Confindustria (SFC). As per SMEs’ requests, to facilitate participation, some of the training sessions were organised in consecutive days and two of them were conducted twice – in Rome by SFC and in Cagliari by RAS – to ensure the widest participation of awarded Italian SMEs.

2.2.1 First training

The first training action was organised by SFC on 22nd March 2022 in Rome and by RAS in Cagliari, Sardinia on 24th March 2022, in a hybrid format (4 hours each; 8 hours in total). The training followed almost the same structure and content for both RAS and SFC although the sessions were given by different experts. The aim was to “replicate” the training to achieve the maximum participation of SMEs’ representatives depending on their needs and time availability. The purpose of this approach was to allow to provide the awarded companies with solid initial theoretical knowledge to start their sustainability path under TOURISME.

The training was focused on Sustainable Development, Circular Economy and Environmental Management as key concepts and principles and their application to the tourism sector. It was aimed at introducing participants to TOURISME and tackling the concepts of sustainable development, circular economy and environmental management and their historical evolution. The training also investigated how these principles informed the development of strategies to address the most salient environmental challenges examining international agreements and regulations to find out how similar approaches are designed to support societal actors. The objective of this first training session was, therefore, to create a level playing field among SMEs, providing them with a set of common knowledge and basic concepts related or applied to the tourism sector such as evolution of tourism, sustainability, circular economy, and competitiveness.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
22/03/2022	Rome & online	14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainable tourism ▪ Definition of sustainable tourism, sustainable development and SDGs ▪ The demand for sustainable tourism ▪ Sustainable tourism in political strategies ▪ Circular tourism ▪ Circular economy and tourism ▪ The measurement of circularity ▪ Environmental management in sustainable tourism ▪ Sustainability as an element of competitiveness for tourism? ▪ Introduction to Business modelling for sustainability
24/03/2022	Cagliari & online	15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Evolution of the tourism from sixties till now ▪ Notion of sustainable tourism, sustainable development, and SDGs ▪ The demand of sustainable tourism and related strategies ▪ Policy of Sustainability of Tourism Circular Economy and Tourism

Figure 5. First & second Italian trainings

2.2.2 Second training

The second training action was organised by SFC on 23rd March 2022 in Rome and by RAS in Cagliari, Sardinia on 25th March 2022 (4 hours each; 8 hours in total). Like the previous training session, it was executed by both RAS and SFC to achieve a greater participation of SMEs.

This training was aimed at enhancing participants' awareness and understanding of the most common environmental standards and labels for products and organisations, to highlight implications of such tools

for tourism. The session examined the most widely adopted international and local environmental certifications. The day opened with an overview on the certification systems, the description of the different types of certifications, their regulatory framework and their application to tourism. It then focused on ECO management system planning, EMAS scheme and, in the context of product certification, it provided an overview of the ECOLABEL scheme. Finally, it gave context explanations about business model canvas for sustainability.

Overall, the main outcome was the alignment of participants' skills and knowledge with respect to scenarios of sustainable business management and opportunities related to the improvement of environmental performance of small businesses in the tourism sector with an increased awareness about environmental certification schemes.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
23/03/2022	Rome & online	16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Certifications, labels, marks, declarations ▪ Process Certifications ▪ Quality Management System (SGA) - ISO 14001 ▪ Eco-Management & Audit Scheme (EMAS) ▪ EMAS & Tourism sector ▪ Product Certifications ▪ Typologies and characteristics: EU Ecolabel, EU Ecolabel and tourism ▪ Introduction to Green purchasing ▪ Additional concepts of Business Modelling for Sustainability
25/03/2022	Cagliari & online	16	<p>Environmental Standards & Environmental Certifications of products/services and organisations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regulatory framework and standardisation ▪ Certification of products and process ▪ How to plan an ECO Management System ▪ EMAS Regulation: How does it works and its benefits ▪ EMAS and Tourism sector ▪ Certification for products ▪ The ECOLABEL ▪ Introduction to green procurement ▪ Introduction to Business Model Canvas

2.2.3 Third training

Organised jointly by SFC and RAS with the support of SSSA, the third training action took place in Rome on 7th April 2022 (5 hours). All Italian companies, both from RAS and SFC SME groups, were invited to participate in the event. The session entailed a review of best practices and case studies in the field of sustainable tourism engagement.

Starting from the Best Practices Map elaborated by TOURISME (>100 practices: <https://tourisme-project.eu/good-practices/>) – task led by SSSA partner, the training session allowed SMEs to know possible practice to reduce the environmental impacts produced by companies operating in the tourism sector and at the same time to support companies in developing a sustainable touristic offer. Sharing the TOURISME best practices allowed the SMEs to become aware of the different actions that could be implemented, in terms of sustainable tourism, and how each practice represented an improvement in the tourism market, both in terms of differentiation and specialisation of the offer, and in terms of savings on the management of the structure.

The ensuing debate between SMEs and experts helped to identify replicability elements and interest in different territories and tourist areas (Travel Agencies and Hotels and accommodation facilities). The meeting also developed two specific sub-sessions: one focused on the issue of food waste, analysing current legislation and practices adopted to reduce this environmental impact; the second focused on Green Procurement in order to increase the knowledge of participating SMEs on how to effectively manage the supply chain. The InCircle project was presented during the meeting to share a tool for self-assessment of sustainable implementation policies in the company.

The outcome of this training action was to make SMEs aware of the opportunities for the innovative development of sustainable tourism practices, to make TOURISME case studies known and addressable by the SMEs benefiting from TOURISME, and to share and dialogue with businesses in order to reason at the same level on the importance of the sustainability of the tourism offer, especially in the phase of relaunching tourism after the pandemic period.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
07/04/2022	Rome & online	22	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainable Tourism Best practices and case studies ▪ TOURISME and good practices for sustainable and circular tourism and their application for SME beneficiaries including discussion and debates between participants and experts ▪ How to start on the path to integrating sustainability and circularity: importance of measurement and some insights from the European project INCIRCLE

Figure 6. Third Italian training

2.2.4 Fourth training

Organised jointly by SFC and RAS, the fourth and last training action for Italy took place in Rome on 8th April 2022 (5 hours). It entailed 3 parallel working sessions to be selected by SMEs based on their needs and interests: 1) Supply chain management: green procurement; 2) Corporate social responsibility & sustainable reporting; 3) Green marketing and green communication.

The topics of the sessions were previously chosen by SMEs. Each SME participated in the selected thematic table, where a facilitator/trainer explored sustainable practice with examples of practical solutions. Individual experiences of SMEs were shared, and participants defined the practical aspects and identified the priority tools, roles, time, resources needed to implement the sustainable practice in their realities.

The outcomes were to foster reflection and debate to support SMEs to make practical but meaningful changes and adaptations of their businesses towards enhanced sustainable practices. The companies appreciated the fact that the workshops' topics could have been previously selected by themselves to find concrete solutions to their real needs and interests.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
08/04/2022	Rome & online	20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Supply chain management: green procurement in tourism sector Green Deal <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Objectives: Decarbonisation, DNSH ○ Approach: LCA ○ Tools: EMS and Labels ○ Means: Green Procurement ▪ Corporate social responsibility and sustainable reporting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The issue of sustainability in tourism and its challenges ○ What is CSR - corporate social responsibility ○ The role of stakeholders: their mapping and management ○ The importance of corporate and sustainability communication ○ Sustainability reporting: the GRI standard ○ Measuring sustainability: indicators ○ The 2030 Agenda and its integration with GRI ○ Discussion sessions to share experiences and perspectives ▪ Green marketing and green communication in the tourism sector <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Analysis of the consumer and its characteristics ○ Market analysis (supply and demand) ○ Greenwashing ○ Environmental claims and European regulatory framework ○ Green Communication plan ○ Communication on Green Certification ○ What can be done in practice?

2.3 Spain

Training actions in Spain have been implemented by the Technological Institute of the Canary Islands (ITC).

2.3.1 Kick off meeting

Like for France, the Spanish responsible partner ITC opted to organise an introductory, optional online kick off meeting with their country's awarded SMEs to present the TOURISME project, meet the participants, discuss the Third-Party Beneficiary Agreement, and agree on a shared activity calendar. The main goal was to get to know each other, explain the objectives of the project, encourage companies to collaborate among themselves, and know their needs and expectations about TOURISME in order to develop the contents that could interest them the most towards the achievement of the project objectives.

Date	Place	Programme
23/12/2021	Online	Presentation of ITC and the TOURISME project Presentation of the awarded SMEs Training and matchmaking planning and preferred content Administrative details incl. Third-Party Beneficiary Agreement

2.3.2 First training

ITC held its first training action (14 hours) on 20th and 21st January 2022 in Madrid to coincide with the International Tourism Trade Fair, FITUR 2022, which was attended by most of the SMEs. The session focused on fundamentals of sustainable tourism and the adaptation of this industry to climate change. To promote sustainable tourism, it was in fact important for businesses to understand the meaning of

sustainability and how traditional tourism activity has caused negative environmental, social and cultural impacts. At the same time, the obligation of companies to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), closely linked to the development of an activity with low environmental impact and more respectful of the social and cultural environment where such activity is established, was explained. A series of low-tech and low-investment tools that can be incorporated into the activity and that together can greatly reduce the impact, both from the point of view of energy efficiency, water saving, waste management using the concept of circular economy, were presented. This first training action was also a meeting point to get to know each other in person for the first time. All participants showed great interest and motivation to turn their businesses around and invest in resources and human resources to develop a more sustainable activity.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
20-21/01/2022	Madrid & online	15	<p>20th January 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visit at FITUR and initial team building <p>21st January 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> TOURISME project summary: duration, budget, members of the consortium, project objectives & phases and beneficiaries Introduction to sustainable tourism and needs identifications Next steps and national and international events of interest

Figure 7. First Spanish training

2.3.3 Second training

The second training action was organised in Tenerife on 27th and 28th April 2022 (7 hours of training and 4 hours of study visits; 11 hours in total), in conjunction with the first Spanish international matchmaking event. The event was attended by the EISMEA Project Officer.

The main goal of this second training was to support SMEs in carrying out an adequate management of the tourism activity including an assessment of the impacts during the exploitation stage. The first day of training was focused on SDGs and the travel industry; ecolabels and greenwashing; and environmental factors in the tourism sector (energy, water, waste, environmental policy and CSR, biodiversity, transportation, etc). It was completed by study visits to good practices in sustainability:

- Winemaking business of Bodegas Monje, offering tourism experiences to bring wine tradition close to tourists. The aim was to learn how a family business with a winemaking tradition has been able to adapt to a tourist offering innovative tourist products to bring the wine tradition closer to tourists;
- Hotel Tigaiga, an example of how to provide a tourist service with minimum environmental impact;

- Town hall of La Orotova presenting the ‘Salitre, Almagre y Azufre’ project based on slow tourism promoted by the city council and created by Patea Tus Montes, an innovative tourism SME from Tenerife that proposes a different way to know the municipality.

On the second day, the training tackled tourism and circular economy and carbon footprint offsetting – zero waste, supplier election, green marketing, and digitalization.

In this event the participants had the opportunity to deepen in the most important factors related to sustainability and to discuss among all the most important aspects to take into account when establishing a more sustainable activity model. Also, SMEs were able to carry out activities that allowed them to get to know each other, learn how each one of them is carrying out these improvements in their respective activities, sharing experiences and knowledge.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
27-28/04/2022	Santa Cruz de Tenerife & online	15	<p><i>27th April 2022</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ SDGs and the travel industry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The 2030 Agenda and the world of tourism ○ Tourism's contribution to the SDGs ○ My company and the SDGs ▪ Ecolabels and greenwashing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What is an ecolabel ○ Why does tourism have so many ecolabels of its own? ○ Are tourism ecolabels a form of greenwashing? ○ Green procurement // sustainable purchasing ▪ Environmental factors in the tourism sector <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy, water and waste ○ Suppliers ○ Environmental policy and CSR ○ Conservation, biodiversity and heritage ○ Carrying capacity ○ Transportation and sustainable mobility ○ Ecological footprint/carbon footprint ▪ Debate on tourism businesses and sustainability: how to integrate it into SMEs ▪ Study visits, good practices in sustainability. <p><i>28th April 2022</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tourism and circular economy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Concept of circular economy ○ Eco design ○ Circular strategies ○ Closing cycles in tourism ▪ Carbon footprint offsetting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Zero waste ○ Supplier selection ○ Green marketing ○ Digitalisation

Figure 8. Second Spanish training, attended by the EC Project Officer (on the left)

2.3.4 Third training

The third training action took place on 26th, 27th and 28th September 2022 in Valencia, hosted at the premises of the Valencia Tourism Centre. In this event, ITC and their SMEs continued to work on the SDGs as a guide to develop a more sustainable activity from an economic, social and environmental point of view and greater understanding on the part of companies for their implementation. The objective of this training was to reaffirm the importance for the company of applying sustainable development objectives when developing a strategy for the development of its activities and because it facilitates access to environmental and sustainability certifications in terms of their implementation in accordance with the required sustainability criteria and parameters. This training showed the SDGs most worked by tourism companies, and the transformation opportunities for companies such as attracting new consumers and increasing satisfaction, adapting to new legislation and taking advantage of research & innovation for the transformation of the sector. An expert from the Global Compact was put at disposal of SMEs to discuss these issues in greater depth and based on each company's reality and needs. Specific sessions about sustainability tools and certifications were also organised, with experts from several organisations to provide guidance.

During the afternoons study visits were planned - one in an urban environment (restoration, accommodation and tour guided visit) and one in a rural environment (accommodation) - to learn first-hand about some of the best practices adopted by companies that already made the transition to offering more sustainable activities and services.

The total duration of the training was:

- 26th September: 4 hours training and workshop and 5 hours for the visits;
- 27th September: 5 hours training and 4 hours for the visits;

- 28th September: 3 hours training and 2 hours for the visits.

With this third event, companies understood the importance of complying with the SDGs to identify whether their social, economic, and environmental impact adds value to society and consequently strengthen their reputation and their relationships with different stakeholders. In the workshops, the companies were able to promote initiatives and new ideas that allow them to improve their management and how to achieve the proposed objectives.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
26-28/09/2022	Valencia & online	27	<p><i>26th September 2022</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Keys to progress in sustainability and the SDGs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Development of business opportunities aligned with SDGs ○ Measuring positive and negative impacts – 2030 Agenda ○ Innovation in products and services contributing to SDGs ○ Contribution of the 2030 Agenda to the tourism sector ○ The three strategic thrusts of the UN Global Compact: learning, visibility and networking ▪ Enterprise Europe Network services for tourism companies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EEN as a driver of growth and employment ○ Services in innovation, internationalisation, access to investments and financing ▪ Workshop <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ For the workshops, two working groups were organized where each group addressed one of these topics: Designing sustainable travel; Communicating sustainability and corporate social responsibility. ▪ Study visits, good practices in sustainability. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Visit to Casa Montaña Restaurant. Casa Montaña is an example of how to implement a Quality and Sustainability Policy aligned with the SDGs ○ Visit to Hotel Balneario Las Arenas, this hotel is an example of how a transformation to a more sustainable business model should be carried out ○ Alternative, sustainable tour more focused on sensory experiences without any impact on the environment <p><i>27th September 2022</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental and sustainability certifications (AENOR, BIOSPHERE and BIOSCORE) ▪ Presentation of tourism sustainability strategy of Valencia in order to make the city a sustainable and intelligent destination ▪ Study visits, good practices in sustainability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hotel Mar de Fulles, where the companies were able to see how a totally ecological hotel is managed. <p><i>28th September 2022</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Study visits, good practices in sustainability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Visit to Las Naves, a centre for social and urban innovation in the city of Valencia, which aims to develop an urban model that improves people's lives from the point of view of sustainability, entrepreneurship and health ▪ Finalisation of training: review of the conclusions of the training and the practical visits

Figure 9. Third Spanish training

2.3.5 Fourth training

The fourth and final training for Spain was organised by ITC in conjunction with the last Spanish matchmaking event to maximise reach-out and impacts and to allow other interested foreign SMEs to benefit from the organised workshops in Madrid.

The training action was implemented across different sub-sessions both online and in face-to-face mode:

- online on 21st December 2022 (1 hour) and 12th January 2023 (1 hour), and
- in presential mode in Madrid on 17th – 18th January 2023.

This fourth training action took place was dedicated to working on the business strategy in terms of sustainability. Once companies were provided with the necessary knowledge to identify their level of sustainability and the measures to be implemented, the last step of their training path was to build an action plan for sustainability in the short and medium term. This training guided companies in developing such a plan. This course helped companies to define concrete and specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and planned actions within a sustainable strategic management model by facilitating: a strategic vision and thinking; a multi-stakeholder approach, and a value chain perspective.

The workshops were facilitated by an expert in Strategic Sustainable Management in companies in coordination with the ITC team. The training was divided into five parts, the first three in virtual format and the last two were face-to-face in Madrid. During the afternoons, several visits were scheduled, one in an urban environment (certified accommodation and guided tour) and another in a rural environment (organic winery), to learn first-hand about some of the good practices adopted by companies that have already implemented actions to offer more sustainable activities and services.

The face-to-face sessions took place at TRIPLE in Madrid, the first HEALTHY Building of co-working and events in Spain, fully committed to ecology and social justice.

In addition to the workshops, as suggested by the same SMEs in previous meetings, several study visits (urban and rural based) were planned to favour peer-learning and discovery of new practices:

- Urban visit, Mo de Movimiento, social project talk, 50% of the team of this restaurant are people at risk of social exclusion;
- Urban visit, tour guided visit in Madrid old town using the tools of sustainable tourism;
- Urban visit, SleepNAtocha, first B-Corp certified accommodation in Spain;
- Rural visit, Viñedo Tierra Calma, organic winery;
- Rural visit, Castillo de la Coracera; and
- Visit FITUR 2023, international tourism fair.

This last training was very positively valued by the companies as it was much more practical than the previous ones. The group work gave the companies the opportunity to put their knowledge to good use and to be able to design an action plan to establish a sustainability policy in their company, and to make proposals for the solution of common problems when implementing these more sustainable practices.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
21/12/2022 12/01/2023 17- 18/01/2023	Madrid & online	17	<p><i>21st December 2022</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Workshop: Videoconference presentation of the contents and dynamics of the training <p><i>Individual work period</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Individual reflection and preparation for the co-creation workshops. Work consisted of giving a questionnaire to each of the companies so that they can reflect on the company's situation in terms of sustainability and what are their expectations and challenges to be met in the short and medium term <p><i>12th January 2023</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Workshop: Videoconference to discuss the previous step and resolve doubts <p><i>17th January 2023</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Co-creation workshop with dynamic and participative teams. In this workshop, companies are divided into groups depending on their level in terms of sustainability <p><i>18th January</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation of results, action planning and timetable for action. In this last workshop, each representative of the different groups will present their sustainability action plan, taking into account the most important aspects for a sustainable strategy, environmental, social, cultural and governance aspects

Figure 10. Fourth Spanish training

2.4 Cyprus

Training actions in the optional country of Cyprus have been implemented by the Nicosia Development Agency (ANEL). Considering the restricted number of involved SMEs and their needs, unlike the other project countries, some of the training sessions were organised only in an online mode.

2.4.1 First training

The first training action promoted in Cyprus was organised online on 1st July 2022 (4 hours) and was focused on an introduction to sustainable tourism. First, SMEs explored the role of tourism in global economy and its environmental impact focusing on Water resources, land degradation / deforestation and intensified or unsustainable use of land, forms of pollution and physical impact of tourism. After this introduction, the session introduced the concept of Sustainable Tourism, its core principles, challenges, and opportunities. Also, the training addressed Sustainable Tourism in relevant EU initiatives and funding programmes, including a special attention to the COSME programme and the newly established Single Market Programme and the role of EU in co-funding projects related to sustainable transnational tourism products. Finally, ANEL presented the TOURISME project more in-depth, and the following steps planned under the different support schemes.

The main outcomes of the introductory training were achieved as the SMEs had the opportunity to familiarise with the terms of Sustainable Tourism and its main principles. SMEs also expressed their experience so far with Sustainable Tourism and what they would be interested to learn about in the future training sessions.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
01/07/2022	Online	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction to Tourism and its role in global economy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Definition Tourism ○ Relevant role in the global economy ▪ Environmental impact of Tourism ▪ Definition of Sustainable Tourism <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Need for Sustainable Tourism ○ Definition of Sustainable Tourism ○ Dimensions of Sustainable Tourism ○ Involvement of the development of sustainable tourism ▪ Principles of Sustainable Tourism ▪ Sustainable Tourism and EU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ COSME / Single Market programmes ○ Projects awarded funding in 2020 ○ The European Tourism Indicators System (ETIS) ○ The EU Ecolabel and EMAS ▪ Project TOURISME <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Objectives, consortium, funding ○ Activities and goals of the project Vouchers and next steps

2.4.2 Second training

The second training action in Cyprus was held on 2nd December 2022 online (4 hours), providing an overview of key practices around Europe, specifically targeting travel agents and hotel accommodation. It was considered valuable to present practices applied in Europe and worldwide for SMEs to develop a better understanding of sustainability in tourism. The overall objective was, therefore, for SMEs to better familiarise with practices of sustainable tourism. The specific objectives of practices of sustainable tourism applied in the hotel industry and travel agency were to present what is already applied in other European countries in order for the SMEs to improve their own facilities or services and discover whether they are already applying sustainable practices. The general feedback of the training was positive as the SMEs had the opportunity to familiarise with green practices and also to explore examples of other countries (such as Slovenia, Cyprus, Greece). It was considered more practical than the first introductory training as through the examples set SMEs recognised practices that they are already applying but also practises that they could apply in the future.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
02/12/2022	Online	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nicosia Tourism Board (Local projects & European projects) ▪ Sustainable and Green Tourism ▪ Objectives of Green Tourism ▪ Decalogue of the Green Tourist ▪ Practices for a «Green» Company ▪ Examples of using Green practices ▪ Other related projects such as “Reducing the Consumption and Disposal of Single-use Plastics in the Tourism Industry in Cyprus, Greece and Malta (SUPMed)”

Figure 11. Online trainings in Cyprus

2.4.3 Third training

The third training action in Cyprus was held on 30th January 2023 in Nicosia at ANEL premises (4 hours) with the objective of deepening SMEs’ sustainable tourism policy. This third part was devoted to tourism companies already engaged in sustainable tourism practices and wishing to deepen their approach to achieve higher levels of environmental performance. The training action tackled sustainability perspectives in the tourism sector in Cyprus, shared experiences and practices as well as promoted a brainstorming discussion through the form of a workshop to set the vision Sustainable future in Cyprus Tourism.

As per feedback received by the participating SMEs, the training was very interesting and interactive as it was conducted face-to-face. Participants had the opportunity to meet other SMEs acting in the same industry and exchange their ideas, current practices. It was also productive that the participants had the chance to express their concerns to the expert and also their difficulties. In general, the workshop was successful as the participants were involved in the training and were able to communicate their interest and uncertainty on some topics.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
30/01/2023	Nicosia (face-to-face only)	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainability in the Tourism Sector – Introduction ▪ Explanation of SDGs under the tourism prism ▪ The Cyprus Tourism Sector and The Sustainability agenda 2030 ▪ Workshop ▪ Exchange of current practices regarding sustainability, concerns and obstacles ▪ Future planning – Goals and planning to achieve the set goals ▪ Challenges of the Cyprus tourism sector

Figure 12. Face-to-face third training in Cyprus

2.4.4 Fourth training

The fourth training action (4 hours) was again held face-to-face in Nicosia at ANEL premises focusing on access to environmental certifications. The objective was to understand the different steps required to access different certification schemes and results achieved were deepened SME’s knowledge for environmental certification; increased knowledge of the steps required to access different certification schemes; and increased awareness of SMEs regarding environmental certifications’ opportunities, experts, and certification bodies specifically in Cyprus. Outcomes of training as per participant’s feedback were positive as the SMEs had the opportunity to enrich their knowledge regarding environmental certifications, to understand the legal background and the EU assessment tools. It was a sufficient base setting for the following activity regarding the certification access.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
22/02/2023	Nicosia (face-to-face only)	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Legal frame- Principles of EU Environmental Law <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EU Legislation on Environmental Assessments ○ Industrial Emissions and accidents ○ EU Waste Law and Policy ○ EU Water Law ▪ Environmental performance management and certification <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EU Environmental Technology Verification (ETV) ○ Eco-management and audit scheme (EMAS) ○ Ecolabel for eco-friendly tourist accommodation ○ Organisation environmental footprint ▪ Access to environmental certification & eco-label <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Definition of the Label ○ Definition of Certification ○ Four of the main labels and certifications in Europe ○ Analysis of four main certifications ○ Competent bodies in Cyprus ○ List of experts / certification bodies in Cyprus

2.5 Conclusions on training support scheme

Training was one of the three support schemes envisaged in the TOURISME capacity building programme for awarded beneficiary SMEs. Training was provided at national level, in each of the involved countries by selected project partners, at times in cooperation with external experts in the field of sustainability and sustainable tourism.

The training support scheme followed a common approach across the countries. The initial training sessions were focused on explaining and discussing foundational concepts of sustainable tourism and their application to companies. This exercise mainly included training about the notion of sustainability, circular economy, corporate social responsibility, and the review of key existing international frameworks for sustainability such as SDGs, the United Nations Global Compact, and the Agenda 2030. As long as the training path was evolving, further practical guidance on how to implement sustainability policies, set up roadmaps at company level and how to reduce carbon footprint in business activities was progressively provided. Special attention was given to the topics of access to environmental certifications and eco labels as well as to technical aspects of the improvement of day-to-day business management that could have favourable impacts on the company’s sustainability.

Both TOURISME partners and SME participants in their trainings' evaluation highlighted the **richness of the contents tackled** throughout the training support scheme. The **most relevant and preferred training topics** based on SMEs' feedback were: processes to access and maintain certifications and eco labels, green procurement, green marketing, solutions and strategies for enhanced communication of sustainability, supply chain management, waste management, planning an environment programme, circular economy and SDGs, and provision of practical steps and examples for adoption of new sustainable practices in the tourism field.

The project managed to find a successful **balance between theoretical content and practical information & specific case studies** to keep SME motivation and engagement high and allow participants to put into practice gathered knowledge. **Good practices** collected and analysed by TOURISME under WP2 were transferred to SMEs during the trainings. Moreover, **study visits and practical case studies** were tackled in numerous training sessions (as well as in the matchmaking events – see Chapter 4) with a positive reception from SMEs. Beneficiaries highly appreciated the possibility to visit sustainable tourism businesses and/or talk directly to experienced entrepreneurs who have been facing similar constraints and problems, both in urban and rural contexts. In addition, sharing practices among the same beneficiaries of TOURISME e.g., using **facilitation and interactive techniques** like workshops, focus groups, brainstorming, etc appeared to be a highly valuable experience. **Peer learning** was an **important aspect of the process towards enhanced sustainability awareness and implementation** for all SMEs. In some cases, by talking to each other, participants could discover innovative practices related to sustainability, feasible to implement in their own realities. Interestingly, a few SMEs also highlighted the fact that thanks to sharing with other companies they realised they were already quite sustainable in their practices. This helped them to increase their awareness in the implementation of their processes and be able to better communicate it to their clients, staff, and providers. Out of the training support scheme experience, the TOURISME consortium can therefore highlight the highly **positive group dynamics** achieved during the sessions. Most of participants were willing to work together, get to know each other, and share ideas and experiences.

Feedback on task 4.1 training retrieved during the training sessions and in the final technical report requested to each participating SME was positive. SMEs showed **satisfaction with the training content**, the structure and the modalities of execution. The training sessions helped SMEs to understand the importance of changing the tourism sector regarding sustainability. They could also learn about different sustainability options and what best practices that could apply to their daily work. **The training and experience of other companies shed light on the fact that opting for a sustainable tourism model is not only a conviction, but the right way to go.** Since the training sessions, they are more aware of the importance of sustainability and have developed new ideas to implement sustainable practices thanks to visiting other companies. They learnt about the benefits of applying sustainability and the importance of involving all members of society. They considered involving their customers in sustainable practices

through education and awareness about the impacts of tourism on the society and environment when they sell a trip.

The main **challenges** the project partners faced in the implementation of the training support scheme were mainly related to the difficulty to balance the load of information with practical sessions and peer learning interaction as a way to keep SMEs' motivation always high during the entire implementation period. Another challenge was that partners had to deal with different levels of awareness and application of environmental management models among their awarded SMEs. While on one hand this diversity allowed for the establishment of highly valuable peer-to-peer learning processes, on the other hand many efforts had to be devoted to structure a balanced training programme to ensure to capture the attention and interest of all participants. Another challenge at the beginning of the implementation of the support scheme was to make companies attend the training sessions onsite. The activities' implementation started yet in challenging moments of the COVID-19 pandemic recovery period, and the extension of the project has had a positive impact of the project support schemes under WP4.

To conclude, the project experience has been positive and has been gradually improving and becoming more and more interactive and interesting throughout the progression of training actions. The second half of the training experience has been the most impactful in all countries. The content was more and more technical and practical, having the SMEs achieved an increased awareness and knowledge on the foundations of sustainable tourism. The improvement of the COVID-19 post-pandemic context allowed to organise field study activities, facilitated travels of SMEs, and ensured closer social interactions and participation. In the last training sessions and in the matchmaking events, SMEs could take the most advantage thanks to their contents and networking.

Training support scheme

Main achievements.

- Richness of content.
- Great diversity of participants.
- Highly positive and active group dynamics .
- Balanced rhythm of the days (theory coupled by workshops & field visits).
- SMEs' willingness to work together and suggestions for training topics.
- Efficient use of facilitation techniques and tools to provide space for peer learning.

Main challenges.

- Difficulties to balance load of information with practical sessions.
- Keep SMEs' motivation and interest always high during the entire process.
- Deal with SMEs with different levels of knowledge and different types of business.

Recommendations for future

- Foresee specific training levels to meet different levels of knowledge and backgrounds of SMEs.
- Coordinate joint training sessions across different participating countries to increase reach-out and avoid duplication.

Improvements for future similar actions and projects emerging from TOURISME experience, from both partners and SMEs, are mainly two:

- Foresee specific training levels to meet different levels of knowledge, as well as different types of activities. TOURISME had to involve both travel agencies and hotels/accommodations within the same support schemes. However, at least a part of the training experience could have been tailored to each business category, especially in the case of travel agencies. This effort was particularly sought in France where many awarded SMEs pertained to this business category.

- Coordinate trainings in the different countries, or perhaps divide the theme or subject to be trained on among all countries participating, to avoid duplications.

The main lesson that all involved parties got at the end of the process is that they have been all involved in a long process and most of them have seen this process as a highly valuable investment. **For SMEs, sustainability seems now to be part of their business strategy in the medium and long term.**

Below some testimonies collected on training scheme from SMEs in the Final Reports are provided:

"Interesting training sessions that allow us to consolidate basic notions of sustainability and sustainable tourism certifications. The most engaging moment for us was to focus on some cases of study because it was positive to look into them and discuss sustainable practices and new business strategies for accommodation and tour operators. It was also good because it was the first time that we got to meet the tour operators involved in a project and create a positive relationship."

FAROO S.R.L., Italy

"We tried to get the best of each training sessions, specially of the ideas created in tasks groups. We have debated and now we believe we have 'planted' the seeds to keep working and growing."

Suncanarias Gestión y Marketing SL, Spain

"The training sessions were interesting and provided us with information needed to identify the situation of our company in regards with environmental sustainability. From now on we want to prioritise environmental sustainability apart from social and economic sustainability."

Viaggi e Miraggi, Italy

"All the training sessions were interesting. Through them, we realised that we were taking some first steps on sustainability, but the process keeps expanding and growing. We also realised that we made some unaware sustainable choices and not communicated them to the public."

Aloha Turia, Spain

"All the training meetings have been very interesting for us; we have learned from all of them and have been able to get to know other experiences and examples of sustainable tourism. We met other Spanish companies and keep in contact with them. The technical visits were very interesting, and we were able to learn from the harsh reality of some small companies that are committed to sustainability."

GENUINE SPAIN, Spain

"The organisation of training workshops was excellent and the content very qualitative."

LIGHT TRIP, France

"It was really interesting to work with international travel agencies and compare goals with each company. I appreciated the speaker and the participatory group format. I learnt a lot about all the causes and effects related to climate and the environment."

Revlys, France

"It was a great opportunity to build solutions as a group and enjoy the work of several minds. Some ideas were really useful to me, mostly about the communication part with clients and providers."

VOYAGEXPERIENCE, France

"Our exchanges with other tourism structures are always very rich. This allows us to place ourselves on the scale of 'good ecological ideas' to be implemented. The visit to the Hotel Zazie in Paris allowed me to reinforce the idea that we are not alone in wanting to do sustainable tourism. Thank you for all these good times and exchanges!"

Gîte de Llo, France

3 Support scheme #2: matchmaking

Under task 4.2, **six matchmaking events** were organised in the three key countries of the project, respectively by L'InstParisReg in France, RAS & SFC in Italy, and ITC in Spain. The matchmaking events included **networking** sessions and the possibility to establish business contacts among the awarded SMEs, while also foreseeing the provision of **additional theoretical knowledge, exchange of practices, peer-learning, field visits, and/or focus groups/workshops with experts**. The events were implemented face-to-face to allow personal contacts among SMEs and, when possible, the theoretical workshops-sessions were web streamed to allow remote connection by companies not able to attend the activities.

As an initial step for task 4.2, WP leader CE produced common guidelines and a calendar template shared in the project folder and accessible to all partners. CE also developed a survey template to distribute among selected SMEs in order to collect information for the matchmaking follow-up, assess satisfaction, and gather feedback for events' improvement.

In addition, WP4 Leader organised an **online technical workshop** with the relevant project partners on 18th February 2022. The aim was to establish the overall approach to matchmaking activities and produce a preliminary calendar for matchmaking event requested by SMEs. The main requirement agreed was that each SME should seek to attend at least 2 matchmaking events. If, due to COVID-19 or other constraints, beneficiaries could travel abroad for both international events, they may attend one national and one international. However, it was important to ensure that at least one international event is fulfilled by SMEs to enable the spending of their travel vouchers.

A description of the implemented activities per country is provided below.

3.1 France

3.1.1 First matchmaking event

The first matchmaking event in France was organised by the responsible partner L'InstParisReg in a hybrid mode on 16th May 2022, in conjunction with the second French SME training. 14 "foreign" (i.e., outside France) SMEs took part in the event. In total, there were 45 attendees.

In the morning of 16th May, participating SMEs and project partners gathered for a workshop named "Building a low carbon & competitive tourism offer". The objective was to help companies gather additional knowledge in this field, and to guide them in the application of the practices. The topics tackled were:

- Mobility and tourism: what levers for the energy transition?
- Carbon offsetting: examples and limits.
- Responsible tourism: diversity and perspectives of development of offers.

In the second part of the seminar, testimonies from travel companies on the steps they have taken were presented:

- 1) French SMEs: Discovery Trains, La Route des Voyages, Odysway, Revlys, Shanti Travel;
- 2) Spanish SMEs: Genuine Spain, Group Los Telares.

Mr. Alan Vella, EC Project Adviser at EISMEA, also had the opportunity to make an online intervention. The morning ended with a presentation of the interactive tool of sustainable good practices developed by L’Institut Paris Region enabling users to discover sustainable tourism practices in a playful and realistic environment. In the afternoon, B2B meetings were held. Representatives from SMEs were invited to sit at a table each. The other representatives were then invited to sit at one of the ten tables for a maximum of 10 minutes of discussion and exchanges. After 10 minutes, they were invited to change tables 4 times. At the end of the afternoon, participants were invited for an urban walk in two different areas of Paris.

In general, participant satisfaction with the matchmaking event was very good, in particular testimonies of SMEs, exchanges opportunities of the different businesses and the keeping of the timing. The seminar in the morning combined with the matchmaking session in the afternoon enriched the whole event thanks to knowledge transfer and knowhow exchanges.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
16/05/2022	Paris & online	45	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mobility and tourism: levers for the energy transition ▪ Carbon offsetting: examples and limits ▪ Responsible tourism: diversity and perspectives of development of offers ▪ Testimonies from travel companies - Discovery Trains, La Route des Voyages, Odysway, Revlys, Shanti Travel, GenuineSpain, Group Los Telares ▪ Intervention of the EC Project Adviser ▪ Masterclasses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Set-up your company in Paris Region ○ Discovering the Paris Region Institute's interactive tool on Sustainable Tourism ▪ Afternoon B2B meetings ▪ Conclusion of the afternoon ▪ Urban walks and social dinner

Figure 13. First matchmaking event in France

3.1.2 Second matchmaking event

The second matchmaking event in France was organised by L’InstParisReg on 13th October 2022 in a fully face-to-face mode, in conjunction with the French SME training. 16 “foreign” (i.e., outside France) SMEs took part in the event. In total, there were 36 attendees.

The aim was first to promote networking. Representatives from SMEs were invited to sit in the conference room or in the entrance hall where armchairs were arranged to facilitate exchanges between all the companies present. Another objective of the event was to further train SMEs on environmental certifications as requested by some companies in the previous matchmaking events. Part of the programme was, therefore, aimed at providing more knowledge on the European eco label, Travel life label for accommodations and HQE label for construction. 6 workshops were organised in parallel, and each participant could participate up to three workshops. Each of them lasted 25 minutes. Participants had 5 minutes to switch from one workshop to another one. The 6 workshops were repeated multiple times and were organised based on feedback experience from SME concerning the adoption of the green key label (Mob Hotel), the Greenhouse gas rating of trips (Le Yogascope) and a solidarity compensation of travels (La Route des Voyages). Finally, the event concluded with a study visit to MOD HOTEL Paris, which is one of the beneficiaries of the TOURISME project to share good practices on sustainability and foster peer-learning among participants.

In general, participant satisfaction was very good; exchanges opportunities of the different businesses and the keeping of the timing. The seminar and matchmaking combined with the workshops and the study visit of the MOB HOTEL (one of the TOURISME SME beneficiaries in Paris) made the event very rich.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
13/10/2022	Paris (face-to-face only)	36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction and recap on TOURISME project, admin reporting, and spending of the voucher ▪ Online presentation on the progress of the project from the Coordinator Consulta Europa ▪ Morning B2B meetings and networking ▪ Afternoon workshops on certifications <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ European ECO LABEL ○ Travel File accommodation ○ Green key ○ ECO Construction ○ Travel and solidarity compensation ○ Greenhouse gas rating of trips ▪ Field visit to one of the beneficiaries (MOB HOTEL based in Paris) to discover their measures put in place (e.g., biological food in the

			restaurant, sober arrangement of rooms, management of waste) to serve as peer-learning for other companies.
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Figure 14. Second matchmaking event in France

Figure 15. Field visit to MOB HOTEL during the matchmaking event

3.2 Italy

3.2.1 First matchmaking event

The first matchmaking event in Italy was organised by Sardinia Region (RAS) in Rimini on 8-9th November 2022 in conjunction with the ECOMONDO Fair – one of the biggest internal fairs for sustainability and ecological transition. This event was also attended by partners who held their periodic project meeting.

The main overall objective of the event was to contribute to expanding SMEs network to institutions and to better select providers of sustainable services and products, while achieving a deeper knowledge of EU opportunities (in terms of networking opportunities and financing programmes) for sustainable SMEs in tourism and on how to measure their sustainable impact to better select which action or certification to implement in coherence with their capabilities and their business activities.

The event was organised in conjunction with ECOMONDO Expo, a reference international event in Europe and the Mediterranean basin for technologies, services and industrial solutions in the green and circular economy sectors, held in Rimini from 7th to 10th November 2022. The purpose of this matchmaking by RAS was to create effective opportunities for SMEs to get in touch with providers participating in the event through a predefined meeting agenda. To do so, RAS arranged with ECOMONDO a registration formula that allowed SMEs to select from the exhibitors catalogue the providers of their interest and manage with them a meeting throughout the Fair duration.

Beyond the networking activities among SMEs and between SMEs and ECOMONDO providers, RAS organised a workshop focused on the opportunities for sustainable development that can be offered from the European framework and to provide SMEs with technical reference on how to measure their environmental impact.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
08-09/11/2022	Rimini (face-to-face)	43	<p><i>8th November 2022</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Context and opportunities for tourism SMEs ▪ TOURISME “Genially” tool, a web application to help implement sustainable tourism practices ▪ Inspiring stories of TOURISME SMEs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Discovery Trains ○ Canarian Hospitality ▪ SMEs in the new EU Single Market Programme 2021-2027: opportunities for European tourism SMEs ▪ Instruments to support European tourism SMEs – the key role of Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) ▪ Living Lab Sharing Good Practices – SMEs Engagement For Sustainability In Tourism: Settlement And Assessment ▪ How to settle and measure sustainability in tourism: the experience of the MEET Network and DestiMED PLUS Projects for the SMEs engagement and the Ecotourism Package Footprint Calculator. Interactive mutual learning session ▪ B2b networking among TOURISME SMEs <p><i>9th November 2022</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Matchmaking and b2b activities pre-scheduled through the participant registration portal between SMEs and ECOMONDO providers ▪ Dissemination of TOURISME project at the stand of Sardinia Region

		<p><i>Meetings with ECOMONDO providers could also be extended until the end of the Fair if relevant for any SMEs.</i></p> <p><i>TOURISME project was showcased by RAS, ACR+, and CE at the Stand of the Region of Sardinia.</i></p>
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Figure 16. First matchmaking event in Italy at the ECOMONDO Fair

3.2.2 Second matchmaking event

The second matchmaking event in Italy – and last one within the project – was organised by Sistemi Formativi Confindustria (SFC) in an eco-sustainable ‘Masseria’, typical of the region of Apulia. The event was held on 22nd and 23rd March 2023, in conjunction with the final consortium’s physical meeting.

The event, as per SMEs’ suggestions, was focused on green marketing and customer perception of sustainable tourism, supporting b2b with experts and testimonials from green marketing networks. The main objective of the matchmaking event was, therefore, to gather know-how and to link with existing networking focused on how environmental certification systems and sustainability plans of SMEs are communicated, and how they are perceived by customers.

The methodology used in this matchmaking event was to put oneself in the customer's shoes, imagining different profiling of the demand for sustainable tourism from the high-level to the more common target oriented.

The first part of the meeting was dedicated to the presentation of the business partner Condè Nast and the sustainability plan it intends to implement in one of the most important high-end tourism networks. The intention was to outline a framework on how green marketing is implemented by other players in the sustainable tourism market, and to trace the strengths and weaknesses of the perception of green marketing from the customer's point of view. Subsequently, elements were introduced for discussion on which green marketing practices are used by TOURISME SMEs, how green marketing can be improved for TOURISME SMEs.

Online testimonials of entrepreneurs engaged in promoting an innovative vision of the tourism sector was ensured, along with some best practices of Green Marketing and Certified Tourism Product. Among them, it is worth mentioning:

- BORGIO PIGNANO, a leader in sustainable luxury hospitality – now Green Globe certified.
- DRAKE BAY GETAWAY, a certified eco boutique hotel.

Participating SMEs were also able to meet and learn from the owner of the Masseria Montenapoleone (the hosting location). One of the specific aspects of this matchmaking event was to allow TOURISME SMEs to have an immersive experience in a sustainable tourism reality. SFC selected an accommodation facility representing a sustainable tourism offer, the Masseria Montenapoleone and asked the owner, Giuliano Monteneve, to present the sustainability plan of the Masseria. This part of the matchmaking event further stimulated constructive dialogue between TOURISME beneficiaries (both accommodation and travel agencies) and a good practice of sustainable tourism. The study visit on the hosting place was split into 2 moments. The first one to know the integrated production systems with the local economy. The second part of the study visit was focused on the merge of technological and cultural aspects for the sustainability of the Masseria. Among their technological solutions there are photovoltaic systems, 0-kilometre catering thanks to the use for cultivation of the land surrounding the Masseria, and water purification systems.

On the second day of the event, the project work continued with networks of enterprises engaged in promoting and supporting sustainable tourism. The meeting presented the impacts of tourism and some effective strategies to differentiate the green tourism offer. The purpose of this session was to imagine sustainability as a path that the company must take, involving the consumer and other relevant and local stakeholders. Furthermore, participants were divided in groups to perform a critical analysis of different communication models, strengths, and proposals for action. Finally, and importantly, all the participants came together with the project partners to assess the overall TOURISME experience, draw conclusions, and agree key steps for sustainability. Feedback emerged from this last workshop has been used to feed the Conclusions Section of the present deliverable.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
22-23/03/2023	Fasano, Puglia (face-to-face only)	26	<p><i>22nd March 2023</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction for participants and recap on SMEs' reporting by Project Coordinator CE ▪ The Sustainable and Certified Tourism Product ▪ The Customer Perception ▪ Presenting and selling the values of a responsible tourism company: the market scenarios ▪ Testimonials of entrepreneurs active in sustainable tourism ▪ Masseria Montenapoleone case study: the green and technological choice ▪ Debriefing & lesson learnt ▪ B2B networking sessions ▪ Social dinner <p><i>23rd March 2023</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainable tourism business across the different accommodation sectors ▪ The green vision and the power of the network: testimonial and case studies: OSPITALITA' NATURA and ACTIVE ITALY ▪ Project work – workshops and further networking ▪ The TOURISME project for SMEs: a shared evaluation on SMEs results and next steps for sustainability

Figure 17. Second matchmaking event in Italy

3.3 Spain

3.3.1 First matchmaking event

The first matchmaking event in Spain took place in Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Canary Islands, from 28th April to 29th April 2022, organised by ITC. The event was held in conjunction with two other project activities: the second training with Spanish SMEs on 27th and the WP1 project meeting with partners in the morning of 28th. In parallel, online matchmaking was kept on the project [b2match platform](#) from 2nd to 24th May. The events were independent of each other, so SMEs could participate in any of them.

The onsite international matchmaking event took place through the entire afternoon of 28th April. Representatives from SMEs were divided into two rooms and invited to stand in a row in front of a peer. They had a maximum of 10 minutes for discussion and exchanges, after which they were invited to change place and meet the following person in the row. This way, everyone was able to exchange with all the companies present.

On 29th April, the participants were invited to take part in a matchmaking activity. The activity was a guided tour in San Cristobal de La Laguna, a declared World Heritage place by the UNESCO, with a tourist guide specialised in sustainability. The detailed agenda, as well as the participants' profile were available at the TOURISME Matchmaking Platform.

During the matchmaking the beneficiaries and project partners, in speed dating activity, had approximately 30 meetings for each participant. The feedback received was very satisfactory from participants, the activities realised during the matchmaking were evaluated very well.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
28-29/10/2022	Tenerife (face-to-face only)	30 (plus 8 project partners)	<p>28th April 2023</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction of Matchmaking event ▪ Project Officer introduction ▪ International Matchmaking event <p>29th April 2023</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Matchmaking activity - Guided tour with tourist guide specialised in sustainability <p>2nd – 24th May 2023</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Online B2B meetings

Figure 18. First matchmaking event in Spain

3.3.2 Second matchmaking event

The second matchmaking event in Spain took place in Madrid on 17th and 18th January 2023, organised by ITC, in conjunction with the FITUR 2023 Fair – the biggest tourism fair for Spain and Latin America. The event took place at TRIPLE - the first HEALTHY Building of coworking and events in Spain, committed to ecology and social justice.

In this latest matchmaking organised by ITC, a series of activities were proposed where the companies not only had the opportunity to work and share knowledge but also to strengthen the bonds between them. The main objective of this event is for companies to deepen their sustainable tourism policy. To this end, all SMEs were invited to attend a workshop to work on the practical application of the scientific model of Strategic Sustainable Management (see Section 2.3.5). Additionally, the matchmaking event included several study visits in Madrid urban and rural areas, as well as the visit to FITUR 2023, the international tourism fair where each company could organise its own agenda of b2b and visit the stands.

As suggested by the same SMEs in previous meetings, several study visits (urban and rural based) were planned to favour peer-learning and discovery of new practices:

- Urban visit, Mo de Movimiento, social project talk, 50% of the team of this restaurant are people at risk of social exclusion;
- Urban visit, tour guided visit in Madrid old town using the tools of sustainable tourism;
- Urban visit, SleepNAtocha, first B-Corp certified accommodation in Spain;
- Rural visit, Viñedo Tierra Calma, organic wineryard;
- Rural visit, Castillo de la Coracera;
- Visit FITUR 2023, international tourism fair.

The feedback received was very satisfactory from participants, and the activities realised during the matchmaking had very good evaluation. This latest event showed that companies were fully aware and had already taken the first steps to develop a new business model by making sustainability a priority. Several SMEs reported that thanks to the event they were able to establish business collaborations with other SME participants and with experts and providers at FITUR Fair.

Date	Place	Attendees	Programme
17-18/01/2022	Madrid (face-to-face only)	67	<p>17th January 2023</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Attendance to the co-creation workshop of the fourth last training action for Spanish SMEs (see further info in Section 2.3.5) ▪ Networking ▪ Urban study visits <p>18th January</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Rural study visits ▪ Networking and b2b matchmaking at FITUR Fair, leading trade fair in the tourism sector and an exceptional forum to promote brands, present new products, learn about the latest trends and get in touch with a multitude of companies related to the sector

Figure 19. Second matchmaking event in Spain

3.4 Conclusions on matchmaking support scheme

Thanks to the implementation of the matchmaking support scheme, SMEs could gain deeper knowledge and contacts through face-to-face interactions and sharing of best practices. The matchmaking support scheme entailed one-to-one meetings with other business peers in a process of exchanging information and experiences as well as ideas on new technologies and innovative solutions and discussing future project proposals and collaborations. The purpose was to make SMEs find business partners and, in some cases like at ECOMONDO and FITUR Fairs, service and products providers.

Overall, SMEs seemed satisfied with the places and contents chosen for the events. The most interesting part for them was to **meet and exchange experiences with other SMEs as well as to deepen the knowledge gathered in the national training sessions and compare it against additional study visits / real case studies**. Dealing with companies that have been active in the world of sustainable tourism for a longer period of time provided less experienced SMEs with useful insights and practical tips for replication. Moreover, the effort in programming different types of activities to make it easy for SMEs to get to know participants (e.g., speed “dating” b2b meetings, field visits, guided tours, testimonies from entrepreneurs, social dinners) seemed to be very much appreciated by beneficiaries.

Workshops, co-creation sessions, and group discussions that were added to the matchmaking events’ agendas enabled participants to further gain knowledge on the development of sustainable offers/stays for their customers and to deepen experience about environmental certifications and eco labels, circular economy approaches, tourism mobility, carbon offsetting, responsible tourism, and green communication. Based on the final reports collected from SMEs, it can be concluded that, in general, the training provided

in the matchmaking workshops was of high quality and helped SMEs to get to know innovative sites in the field of sustainability.

Almost all SMEs from France, Spain and Italy participated in at least 2 matchmaking activities. There were several companies which were very active and ensured their participation in more than two events (without overpassing the given Voucher amount). The matchmaking support scheme contributed to **establish new international and national business contacts and partnerships**. Based on the final reports completed by SMEs, it can be highlighted that **over 60% of them confirmed they were able to establish or start to establish collaborations and partnerships thanks to task 4.2 activities**.

Matchmaking support scheme

Main achievements

- Peer learning and proactive group dynamics.
- Creation of synergies and business connections.
- Exchange of good practices.
- More in-depth knowledge beyond training incl. additional study visits.

Main challenges

- Diverse profile and level of expertise of SMEs.
- COVID-19 recovery period.

Recommendations for future

- Open matchmaking events more to external stakeholders (buyer-supplier approach).
- Create networking opportunities and space (e.g., platform) to allow the connection of all tourism SMEs involved in the Cascade grants.

To conclude, matchmaking activities were an opportunity for team building and relating with potential clients during the fairs and to create partnerships with the TOURISME project partners. During workshops and field visits, SMEs were able to co-create new ideas and share strategies. **The matchmaking support scheme was successful in creating synergies and exchange of good practices between SMEs in Europe**. Beneficiaries increased their knowledge and widened their network in the field of sustainable tourism and shared what are their environmentally friendly solutions.

Based on the implementation of the TOURISME experience and the feedback collected from partners and SMEs, the **key recommendation** for future similar initiatives / projects is to foresee a wider participation of external SMEs and other stakeholders from the supply chain, such as outbound agencies, service providers, buyers, etc. As per Grant Agreement, the TOURISME matchmaking scheme was meant to forge synergies mainly between the awarded SMEs as a way to increase awareness and implementation of sustainable tourism practices and knowledge and create business contacts. To a certain extent, external stakeholders were involved in the project in the form of experts, case studies, certification & service providers, especially in the two matchmaking events organised in connection with the international fairs of FITUR and ECOMONDO. Nevertheless, for future projects, it could be envisaged to strengthen the “buyer-supplier” approach to seek to achieve greater commercial partnerships as well as plan joint matchmaking actions with EU sister projects and their SMEs.

Moreover, as highlighted by the same SME beneficiaries, it could be interesting for the Funding Agency EISMEA to set up a network of all companies involved in the Cascade grants to support tourism to promote periodic networking events among them either online or physically in Brussels. Also, it could be interesting

in the future to have a common platform open to the involved SMEs participating to share knowledge and experiences.

Below are some testimonies about matchmaking support scheme, collected from SMEs in their Final Technical Reports:

"We have learnt the needs and challenges of SMEs involved in the project and explored networking. Overall, it was amazing for a small company to be able to attend all these international events."

GENUINE SPAIN, Spain

"The idea of sharing this time with professionals and companies of tourism that belong to different fields like hotels, travel agencies, etc was interesting and inspiring. Paris matchmaking was very important for me because, for the first time, I was meeting SMEs of the other countries. The certification workshops proposed at the event were useful to know what certifications were being chosen for accommodations in the different countries and assess which could be the best certification path for my business."

Inzulae SLU, Spain

"If we all want to be more sustainable and develop our business in accordance with modern requirements, it is necessary to exchange and share not only information but also practices that give both positive and negative results. And these events gave them the opportunities to develop more efficiently in changing conditions, allowing to see experience of colleagues in other countries, to know and adopt new tools in tourism."

DYADYA VANYA SL, Spain

"In Madrid we had the opportunity to meet highly competitive and successful companies and the activities and presentations have allowed us to deepen in practical aspects examined during the training sessions. The ECOMONDO event in Rimini was also an excellent opportunity to know how the market is oriented towards sustainable products and services."

VLVI' DI MASSIMO VIOLINI, Italy

"We could gain knowledge and ideas thanks to face-to-face interactions and sharing and adoption of best practices."

HOTEL VILLAGE SUVAKI, Italy

"Be part of TOURISME project and participate at the Matchmaking events helped us to discover all the labels and choose the right one for our hotel."

Duo Hotel, France

"I was very glad as well to hear some testimonies from different travel companies. It gave insights on how to implement some actions in order to lower the carbon emission. FITUR - tourism Madrid world fair: it was great to go to the fair and meet some Japan tourism business players, to be able to make partnerships with Japan experience as an office in Madrid."

JAPAN EXPERIENCE, France

"During these meetings, I had the opportunity to discuss with companies that had already taken the steps to obtain labelling as a green key. I was able to learn about all the topics covered and take advice and recommendations. These exchanges have been essential in our sustainable tourism journey. This allowed us to centralize our ideas, our actions, and our point of view to get the best out of them."

VAL DE ROLAND, France

"The chosen location for the last matchmaking was the Masseria Montenapoleone in Apulia, particularly inspirational, as being totally committed to sustainable tourism. It was the worthy conclusion of a project. It helped me understand the need for effective communication of sustainability at two levels: towards the customer but also towards employees who then transmit everything to the guest."

Bed And Ocean, Spain

4 Support scheme #3: certifications

Access to
environmental
certifications

The third support scheme envisaged by TOURISME was related to environmental certifications under task 4.1. It aimed at facilitating understanding and access to different EC initiatives promoting sustainable tourism, such as EU ecolabel and/or different national and international environmental certifications such as Green Key and Biosphere. This was carried out, on the one hand, through activities organised in task 4.1 (and 4.2, when applicable), and, on the other hand, through tailored mentoring and advisory services to interested tourism SMEs.

The scheme was optional, and SMEs could choose it at the time of application for the EU funding. **Out of the 65 selected SMEs, 48 opted for the certification voucher when applying to the TOURISME Call. In addition, other 4 decided to engage in this activity later on in the project, without increasing the amount of the already awarded funding.** This proves the relevance of such a support scheme and confirms how TOURISME training path could convince beneficiary SMEs to see sustainability as a new relevant aspect of their business strategy and roadmap.

The financial support to SMEs envisaged for this support scheme was at least €1.000 in Spain, Italy, and France and €600 in Cyprus, provided via a Certification Voucher. The voucher was used to sustain costs related to individual mentoring and advisory services from experts, consultants, and/or certification providers, as well as costs of new certification/standardisation or maintenance of certification.

This voucher was particularly appreciated by SME beneficiaries considering that certifications costs are often expensive and time-consuming to implement by a small and medium enterprise. Later in the project, it was also decided that if an SME had unspent travel costs from the other support schemes, unused funds could be transferred to the certification voucher where costs were higher. Thanks to the certification voucher, SMEs could count on the support and mentoring of not only the project partners but also dedicated external consultants and experts to help SMEs set up their environmental strategies, the preparation of internal processes and tools to receive the audit for the certification.

At the start of the project experience, most of companies that applied to the TOURISME call for funding did not have any environmental certification scheme implemented. Only few were certified, mainly medium size accommodation structures. At the time of the call for proposals' presentation, the applicants were asked whether they had already adopted certifications such as EMAS, EU Ecolabel, and ISO certifications such as ISO 9001, ISO 14001, ISO 22000, ISO 50001, ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001, etc. As there are various certifying bodies and schemes in different countries, applicants were also asked to inform whether they had adopted any sector-specific certifications or other certifications recognised in their respective countries. Furthermore, applicants were asked to declare whether they would be interested to access environmental certification. Lastly, applicants were asked to declare whether they were already implemented any of the listed sustainability practices and which sustainability practices they would be interested to implement during the TOURISME project being beneficiary (or selected) SMEs. It is worth mentioning that sustainability practices could vary for accommodations and travel enterprises and therefore two slightly different survey questionnaires were papered.

As reported in Deliverable 3.4 – Benchmarking Sustainability of Selected SMEs, the initial status of certifications was very poor in selected SMEs. Only 1 out of 40 selected accommodations declared to have adopted ISO 14001 while the rest of the ISO certifications are not yet adopted by selected accommodations. However, 4 out of 40 selected accommodations adopted EU Ecolabel. However, although most of the selected SMEs did not have adopted any sort of certifications, many were willing to participate in the Certifications Support Scheme in order to access certifications. 36 out of 40 selected accommodations explicitly stated that were interested to access certifications. On the other hand, 17 out of 22 selected travel enterprises expressed their interest to access certifications while 5 selected travel enterprises are not interested in doing so.

One of the key outcomes of the TOURISME project was to support tourism SMEs in transitioning towards sustainability. Overall, the selected beneficiaries have shown high motivation to implement sustainability practices and to approach access to environmental certifications. To achieve this objective, TOURISME partners planned dedicated training and mentoring actions within the framework of their task 4.1 trainings and task 4.2 matchmaking events. Under WP4, it was decided to conduct at least one training from task 4.1 dedicated to certifications and/or EC initiatives for sustainable tourism. In addition, it was agreed that, whenever relevant, matchmaking events could entail sessions aimed at environmental certifications' awareness and peer learning and best practice sharing to facilitate access to such certifications.

Thanks to the knowledge gathered in training and matchmaking support schemes, companies applying for the TOURISME certification vouchers were able to establish their own path for the access to environmental certifications, or their maintenance in few cases. Project partners and involved experts supported the companies in the identification of the most suitable certifications. Mentoring and consulting services through the certification voucher allowed the definition of the key steps to set up the right processes at internal level and to prepare the certifications' applications.

The certifications and labels chosen by TOURISME SMEs have been different including international/European and national ones according to the needs and preferences of each enterprise. The most recurrent certifications, labels, and initiatives have been:

- Ecolabel
- Green Key
- Biosphere
- Travel Life
- Biorismo
- ISO 14001:2015
- Label AB - Agriculture Biologique

Additional ones selected by a few SMEs have also been:

- EMAS
- ISO 17033:2019
- Ecostarts
- BCorp
- Passivhaus
- Legambiente Turismo

- ATR (Agir pour un tourisme responsable)

Certification path and changes in sustainable practices of a business require a long process and long-term commitment. Based on the results of final reporting, it can be highlighted that **26 SMEs have managed to achieve an environmental certification or are in the latest finalisation stage for obtaining it¹**. Some even have achieved more than one certification. The rest of companies are working to progress on their sustainable practices to comply with certifications' criteria and preparing for audits.

<i>No of SMEs accessing certifications</i>	<i>No and Type of certification</i>
FRANCE	
4 SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Green Key: 3 ▪ Biorismo: 1 ▪ Label AB – Agriculture Biologique: 2
ITALY	
9 SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ECOLABEL: 5 ▪ Green Key: 2 ▪ ISO 14001: 2 ▪ Legambiente turismo: 1 ▪ Green tourism: 1
SPAIN	
13 SMEs <i>(4 achieved and 9 in finalisation of certification stage)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biosphere: 9 ▪ Trave Life: 3 ▪ Green Key: 1 ▪ S Sostenibilidad Turística (ICTE): 1

The certification process varied for each SME, largely depending on their type of economic activity and their previous knowledge and experience in the processes of sustainability and certification schemes. For some beneficiaries, it took more efforts than expected to figure out the correct path and the most suitable certification type to pursue. For others, especially larger accommodation realities, the process was more straight forward. The case of travel agencies was more challenging since there are no specific environmental certifications specifically adapted to the activity they conduct.

In conclusion, thanks to the work performed under task 4.3, SMEs understood the importance of work with a method, to define, write and share protocols for action, to define goals and monitor process and impacts; the need to share and involve the whole team; and the relevance of communication of sustainability both internal and external. The TOURISME experience was a capacity building and mentoring process to help SMEs to understand more about environmental certifications, convince them about their relevant for both sustainability but also business purposes. Also, a lesson learnt by the project has been that such a pathway is more easily and faster to implement when shared with others.

¹ E.g., received the "COMMITTED" category of the certification and about to access the final audit; or waiting for the conclusive outcome of the final audit.

5 Conclusions

The TOURISME project developed and implemented schemes for tourism SMEs in three main pilot countries (Italy, France, and Spain) plus in another fourth optional one (Cyprus). These schemes were built around three core activities dedicated to promoting transnational cooperation among other SMEs and stakeholders, increasing capacity building skills and facilitating access to environmental certifications. The first activity foresaw the organisation of trainings and capacity building sessions. In the second one, international matchmaking b2b events were organised, while also deepening knowledge gathered through the trainings at national level. Lastly, a third, optional activity entailed specific support to promote and facilitate access to environmental certifications and to other EC initiatives such as EU Ecolabel.

The training part of the TOURISME programme helped SMEs to have a broader vision on the main issues related to sustainable tourism and on how to develop a working plan in order to implement relevant actions for sustainable growth. SMEs received theoretical background to build the foundations and get familiarised with the rationale for enhanced sustainability in the tourism industry, while also receiving practical mentoring, ad hoc recommendations on key topics related to sustainability and being engaged in peer learning processes through study visits, best practices' sharing, case studies' analyses, b2b interactions with other fellows at national and international levels, etc.

SMEs had the opportunity to assist to multiple training sessions and workshops about different tasks of sustainable tourism. They could learn about a variety of applications of sustainable tourism and initiatives, which helped them plan and implement different environmental, social, and economic development actions within their businesses. Beneficiaries also learnt about the experiences of other SMEs with regards to sustainable development. They could get clearer ideas on how to reduce the impact of their business activity on local communities and the environment; moreover, they were able to develop a plan to make an optimal use of resources, avoid over-consumption, helping with the conservation of the natural surrounding and making a conscious effort to respect local traditions and heritage, as well as contributing to their preservation. This meant for them planning and setting a roadmap for more sustainable methods of business management, as well as give recommendations and support to guests and employees to avoid harmful activities to local environment. Learning about the activities and objectives of European companies in the field of sustainability seemed to have opened up areas for improvement among the project beneficiaries.

The matchmaking events helped beneficiaries to meet other companies and share ideas, concerns and future plans with foreign fellow SMEs and other stakeholders e.g., best practices' representatives. Most SMEs in TOURISME were not yet experts on issues of sustainable tourism and faced similar problems in the transition toward a more sustainable business activity, especially in terms of budget constraints. Beneficiaries found particularly inspiring to hear stories of other SME managers and staff dealing with sustainable transition, and they also found it useful to understand which kind of economic solution they put in practice for the implementation of relevant actions. In addition, they benefited from the opportunity to strengthen their relationship with other European companies and to start creating links or set up business collaborations. It is worth noting that some SMEs had not had the opportunity to meet foreign peers before the TOURISME experience. Matchmaking was therefore a particularly enriching experience to broaden their views and contacts.

The certification scheme was the third part of the TOURISME capacity building programme and dealt with the increased knowledge and roadmap establishment for the access to environmental certifications by SMEs. The scheme seemed to have been appreciated by beneficiaries given the fact that it provided financial contribution for certifications' access, which is normally an expensive and time-consuming activity. Through the TOURISME certification voucher, SMEs could get support of experts, consultants or certification provides to establish a strategy for environmental certification access (or maintenance in few cases). The training on environmental certifications/labels helped SMEs to understand the importance of working within an official national or international certification framework for sustainable growth.

Towards the end of TOURISME, the project partner organisations promoted a joint workshop with SMEs to discuss the TOURISME experience and set the roadmap for its legacy. The workshop was held in the final matchmaking event held in Apulia, Italy on 23rd March 2023. Based on the workshop outcomes, along with the reflections of project partners and the feedback of the SMEs' final reports, it can be concluded that the TOURISME support scheme experience has managed to streamline a new vision in SMEs to change their mindsets for sustainable growth and strive for more environmentally respectful behaviours and processes. The project activities represented a fresh start for involved SMEs, helping them to set up their roadmap for sustainability through the collaboration with TOURISME partners, companies and experts from different countries.

Knowledge sharing and peer learning have been powerful tools promoted by the project to increase SMEs' awareness on sustainability and support the uptake of new practices and the set-up of an internal strategy for sustainability. For continuation after the project, it was agreed with SMEs to maintain alive the TOURISME LinkedIn SME Group. Management will be up to the Coordinator CE supported by partners to issue periodic updates on sustainable tourism and related EU initiatives and projects, keep the conversations ongoing, and make periodic follow-ups to maintain alive the connections. Moreover, it was agreed that a joint database with contacts and profiles of involved SMEs will be also drafted and shared among the beneficiaries building on and expanding the information already used for the [Beneficiary SMEs Map](#) on the TOURISME website. This shall help SMEs to stay in contact and further growth the collaborations and contacts established during the project events. Moreover, core training materials on sustainable tourism emerged from the project support schemes will be showcased on the project website and widely disseminated. The project website will be kept alive after the project's end.

To conclude, the support scheme approach for enhanced tourism SMEs' awareness and capacity building in sustainability seems to be a relevant action to keep continuing to implement at local or European level, with clearly direct positive impacts on the involved participants. Lately, tourism industries and businesses have been dealing with an increasing pressure and demand for improving their environmental performances and for green transition; however, many times they do not yet have the sufficient capacity and knowledge. SMEs cannot simply achieve enhanced sustainability all alone, but it is important that relevant organisations e.g., public bodies and intermediary business organisations provide skills' support via capacity building, peer learning, practical mentoring, and direct financing for certifications. The support scheme methodology can be an effective way to ensure guidance and provide knowledge basis for the green transition of the tourism sector. The combination of training, matchmaking, and certification schemes have resulted in a meaningful experience for TOURISME SMEs, and the project can conclude that the approach shall be sustained in the longer term, also considering the reflections and recommendations discussed in the previous sections of this report.

ANNEXES

Annex I – Training & Matchmaking Reports for project partners

Annex II – Satisfaction survey templates

Annex III – Templates for SMEs' reporting

Annex I – Training & Matchmaking Reports for project partners

Training

Task 4.1 Face-to-face and online capacity building trainings and mentoring

In the framework of Task 4.1, trainings are expected to be delivered in Spain, Italy, France, and Cyprus. All instructions and key requirements in line with the call for SMEs are outlined in the document “Training Planning”, available on the project repository. Selected SMEs receive financial support in the form of Training Vouchers to take part in the training courses organised by TOURISME partners in their countries.

For each training (already organised) please provide the following information and send this template filled out back to the WP4 leader/Coordinator max. within 3 weeks after the finalisation of the activity.

[Insert here name of your institution]

Training outline
<p>Training title & main topic(s) tackled</p>
<p>Format <i>[Only physical, Hybrid, Only online] please carefully revise instructions in the “Training Planning” document and bear in mind that at least 3 out of 4 trainings must be physical to allow SMEs to spend the awarded money; the ideal scenario is to implement all trainings in-person while providing online option for any participants that might not be able to travel e.g., due to COVID-19 restrictions]</i></p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Only physical <input type="checkbox"/> Hybrid <input type="checkbox"/> Only online </p>
<p>Rationale for the training <i>[why there is a need for this training]</i></p>
<p>Objectives of the training <i>[what is intended to achieve with the training]</i></p> <p>Overall objective:</p> <p>Specific objectives: <i>Explain the specific objectives of the training programme, addressing the objectives of each of the modules included.</i></p>
<p>Structure and proposed duration of the training</p> <p>Total duration of the training: <i>[total number of hours]</i></p> <p>Period on which the training takes place: <i>[include starting date and ending date]</i></p> <p>Location where the training takes place: <i>[include the venue]</i></p>
<p>Content <i>[Include the main content covered]</i></p> <p>Example: Session 1: <i>[Name of session 1]</i> 1.) XXX 2.) XXX 3.) XXX Session 2: <i>[Name of session 2]</i> 1.) XXX 2.) XXX</p>

3.) XXX
Material [detail the material you have generated for the training (PPT presentations, infographics, guidelines, etc.)]
Expert(s) involved [detail the experts involved in the training by briefly describing their expertise; please clarify if they were external or from your own staff]
Attendance Number of SMEs attending the training: [SMEs attending the training] Number of attendees: [participants attending the training]
Tools and techniques used [only if applicable, detail any tool/technique used to facilitate the sessions, participants' presentations or discussions e.g., ice breaking games]
Dissemination of the training [Please report how the event was disseminated on your own institutional media channels and the TOURISME channels; if possible, please include the links to the news/posts]
Overall conclusions/outcomes of the training and participants' feedback [please report 1) main outcomes and conclusions of the training and 2) satisfaction rates and, if applicable, most relevant feedback from participants retrieved from the satisfaction survey you have circulated among them. Please remember to keep the answers of the survey in your own records]
Challenges, lessons learnt & next steps [if any, please briefly mention main challenges for the organisation/delivery of the training, key lessons learnt for next activities' organisation / improvements]
Agenda
[include here the final agenda including timing for each session/slot of the training]

Matchmaking

Task 4.2 Matchmaking SMEs

In the framework of Task 4.2, two matchmaking events will be organized in Spain (ITC), Italy (SFC, RAS), France (L'INSTITUTE PARIS REGION) and Cyprus (ANEL). All instructions and key requirements in line with the call for SMEs are outlined in the document "Matchmaking Planning", available on the project repository. Selected SMEs receive financial support in the form of Matchmaking Vouchers to take part in the events organised by TOURISME partners in their countries.

For each matchmaking event (already organised) please provide the following information and send this template filled out back to the WP4 leader/Coordinator max. within 3 weeks after the finalisation of the activity.

[Insert here name of your institution]

Matchmaking event outline
<p>Event title</p>
<p>Format</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Fully physical</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Hybrid <i>(please select this option only if you offered online access to the event along with in-person activities)</i></p>
<p>Rationale for the matchmaking <i>[why there is a need for this event]</i></p>
<p>Objectives of the matchmaking <i>[what is intended to achieve with the event]</i></p> <p>Overall objective:</p> <p>Specific objectives: <i>Explain the specific objectives of the event and highlight if you have focused on a specific topic for the matchmaking event (not compulsory). Please also clarify if the event is organised in conjunction with any local/national fairs/conferences.</i></p>
<p>Structure and proposed duration of the event</p> <p>Number of hours of the event: <i>[include hours of the matchmaking event]</i></p> <p>Period on which the event takes place: <i>[include starting date and ending date]</i></p> <p>Location where the event takes place: <i>[include the venue]</i></p>
<p>Content <i>[Include the main content covered]</i></p> <p><i>Example:</i></p> <p>Session 1: <i>[Name of session 1]</i></p> <p>1.) XXX</p> <p>2.) XXX</p> <p>3.) XXX</p> <p>Session 2: <i>[Name of session 2]</i></p> <p>1.) XXX</p> <p>2.) XXX</p> <p>3.) XXX</p> <p><i>[If your event is organised in conjunction with any local/national fairs/conferences taking place at the same time, please describe the relevant connection between the two]</i></p>
<p>Material <i>[detail any material you have generated for the event (PPT presentations, infographics, guidelines, etc.)]</i></p>

<p>Attendance</p> <p>Number of foreign SMEs attending the event: <i>[SMEs from other countries than yours that have attended the event]</i></p> <p>Number of attendees: <i>[total number of participants that have attended the event]</i></p> <p><i>Please include the number of national SMEs only if the event is attended by any companies from your own country: [SMEs from your country if applicable. E.g., some partners are organising the matchmaking activity in conjunction with their national training to give national SMEs the possibility to meet their international peers. In this case, you would need to clarify in this row how many SMEs from your country attended the matchmaking]</i></p>
<p>Tools and techniques used <i>[only if applicable, detail any specific tool or facilitation technique used to promote exchange of practices and ideas and networking]</i></p>
<p>Dissemination of the event <i>[Please report how the event was disseminated on your own institutional media channels and the TOURISME channels; if possible, please include the links to the news/posts]</i></p>
<p>Overall conclusions/outcomes of the event and participants' feedback <i>[please report 1) main outcomes and conclusions of the event and 2) satisfaction rates and, if applicable, most relevant feedback from participants retrieved from the satisfaction survey you have circulated among them. Please remember to keep the answers of the survey in your own records]</i></p>
<p>Collaborations achieved</p> <p><i>If any, please briefly describe if collaborations / partnerships were established within participants and, if possible, provide details (e.g., type, number) in this regard.</i></p>
<p>Challenges, lessons learnt & next steps</p> <p><i>[if any, please briefly mention main challenges for the organisation/delivery of the event and key lessons learnt for next activities' organisation / improvements]</i></p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Agenda</p>
<p><i>[Include here the final agenda or copy the link of the agenda available in the b2match platform if eventually we can purchase this tool]</i></p>

Annex II – Satisfaction survey templates

Training

TOURISME Training – Satisfaction Survey

On behalf of the TOURISME project and the partner organising the event, we thank you for your attendance in the training and we hope you had a valuable experience.

To help us track progress and improve activities, we would like to hear your opinion.

To fulfil this, please answer this short satisfaction survey. It will take 5 minutes. Thank you for your contribution!

In which country is your SME based?

- Cyprus
- France
- Italy
- Spain

Which TOURISME event have you attended? Please include the training's title & dates and the hosting organisation from TOURISME.

Please indicate your level of satisfaction with the training in general

- Very satisfied
- Satisfied
- Quite satisfied
- Not satisfied

Please evaluate your level of satisfaction with the following aspects:

Q1. Structure and overall design of the training

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q2. The depth which the different topics have been addressed

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q3. The usefulness of the training for professional practice

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q4. Quality of presentations / speakers

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q5. Level of interaction among participants

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q6. Pre-event organisation and support to prepare your travel

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q7. Venue's facility and on-site organisation and support

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Comments (optional)

What did you most appreciate during the training?

Do you have any recommendations for the improvement of the organisation of the next training(s)?

In future training actions, what other topics would you like us to offer?

Thank you for your feedback!

Online version available here:

Matchmaking

TOURISME Matchmaking – Satisfaction Survey

On behalf of the TOURISME project and the organising partner, we thank you for your attendance in the matchmaking event and we hope you had a valuable experience.

To help us track progress and improve activities, we would like to hear your opinion.

To fulfil this, please answer this short satisfaction survey. It will take 5 minutes. Thank you for your contribution!

In which country is your SME based?

- Cyprus
- France
- Italy
- Spain

In which country have you attended the matchmaking event?

- Cyprus
- France
- Italy
- Spain

Which TOURISME event have you attended? Please include the matchmaking's title and/or the hosting organisation name and the dates.

Please indicate your level of satisfaction with the event in general

- Very satisfied
- Satisfied
- Quite satisfied
- Not satisfied

Please evaluate your level of satisfaction with the following aspects:

Q1. Structure and overall design of the event

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q2. Level of interaction and networking among participants

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q3. The usefulness of the event to create partnerships/synergies business-to-business

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q4. The usefulness of the event to facilitate the exchange of good practices and/or technical skills transfer

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied

- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q5. Pre-event organisation and support to prepare your travel

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Q6. Venue's facility and on-site organisation and support

- Excellent - Very satisfied
- Good - Satisfied
- Fair - Quite satisfied
- Insufficient – Not satisfied

Comments

Have you managed to establish (or start working on) collaborations/partnerships? If so, please describe which ones.

What did you most appreciate during the event? (optional)

Do you have any recommendations for the improvement of the organisation of the next matchmaking event(s)? (optional)

Thank you for your feedback!

Online version available here:

Annex III – Templates for SMEs’ reporting

Technical report template - SMEs

TOURISME Final Technical Report

INTRODUCTION

<i>Project:</i>	TOURISME
<i>Project Grant Agreement No:</i>	951103
<i>SME legal name:</i>	
<i>SME business name (if different from above):</i>	
<i>SME identification number (e.g., registration / VAT number):</i>	
<i>Country:</i>	
<i>Author of the report (name & position):</i>	

Please fill out the corresponding table(s) following the given instructions:

ACTIVITY 1. TRAINING

Please report on your participation in the Activity-1 Training actions

<i>Training attended</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Venue [please specify if attended online]</i>	<i>People participating (names, functions)</i>

Please tell us about your training experience: key outcomes, perceptions, lessons learnt, and any other comments on the results of training activities

Max. 2,000 characters

ACTIVITY 2. MATCHMAKING

Please report on your attendance to matchmaking events.

<i>Matchmaking attended</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Venue [please</i>	<i>People participating</i>
-----------------------------	-------------	----------------------	-----------------------------

		<i>specify if attended online]</i>	<i>(names, functions)</i>

Please tell us about the matchmaking events’ experience: perceptions, key outcomes, contacts, and results and any other comments on the results of activities.

Max. 2,000 characters

Thanks to the attended matchmaking events, have you managed to establish / or have you started to establish any partnerships, agreements, and/or new business contacts? Please select the correct answer below.

Please select

If yes, please state the name(s) of the relevant SME(s).

ACTIVITY 3. CERTIFICATION

Please briefly describe the activities implemented under Activity 3. Please report on the type of certification(s) sought, the activities implemented to achieve the certification(s) including mentoring/consulting if applicable. Please also describe the providers/consultants you collaborated with (if any) and please report the key progresses and outcomes.

Name of certification(s) / label(s) sought or achieved:
Activities implemented to achieve (or maintain) the certification e.g., consulting service:
Provider(s)/Consultant(s) involved:

Outcomes achieved (please clearly state if a certification was achieved or maintained; if not, you can explain main learnings & outcomes of your certification path:

FINAL REMARKS

Please report key best practices and/or sustainable improvements achieved thanks to the TOURISME project and any other final remarks you would like to share with us.

<i>Max. 1,500 characters</i>

Signature and stamp

Name: Position: [add signature and stamp]

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The content of this publication represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility; it cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission and/or the Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (EASME) or any other body of the European Union. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.

TOURISME

Boosting Sustainable Tourism Development and Capacity of Tourism SMEs through Transnational Cooperation and Knowledge Transfer

 Co-funded by the COSME Initiative of the European Union

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